

putting research knowledge at the heart of development

Daily Research Challenges in African Laboratories

The African continent is increasingly being represented within international scientific research. Every year there are an increasing number of peer-reviewed articles published by African scientists. Key to this increasing research outputs are better funding for projects, growing networking possibilities and increased availability of online resources.

Nonetheless, for many researchers in African laboratories, more can be done. In particular, the shortage of core funding to maintain and improve research environments causes many challenges for day-to-day research activities. Being able to address these issues in the laboratory research environments can thus have significant implications for *speeding up* research productivity and outputs.

As yet, however, there is little data on the challenges faced by African scientists in daily research activities. In particular, self-reports from scientists working "on the ground" are vital for future funding and regulatory conversations. This survey will address this deficit by giving scientists in Southern Africa the opportunity to highlight issues that challenge their research activities. In effect, we would like to know what slows down or speeds up your research activities? What makes them stop?

This survey is designed from interviews conducted by scientists in South Africa and Kenya. If you feel that the questions do not reflect your current working environment, please use the open text boxes to tell us a bit more about your current situation.

Project information

This project is run by Dr Louise Bezuidenhout (University of the Witwatersrand, South Africa) and Dr Ereck Chakauya (NEPAD-SANBio). The survey is funded by INASP (International Network for the Availability of Scientific Publications).

This survey is entirely voluntary and anonymous. The completion of the survey is taken as consent for the inclusion of the data into the final dataset. The findings of this survey will contribute towards

academic publications and conference presentations. The findings will also feature on websites such as those run by NEPAD-SANBio and INASP.

For more information on the project or the findings, please contact Dr Louise Bezuidenhout at louise.bezuidenhout@wits.ac.za

1. Before you start the survey please let us know something about yourself.

I am a ...

- Professor
- Lecturer/Researcher
- Postdoctoral researcher
- Postgraduate student

2. I work at a ...

- University
- College
- Government research facility
- Independent research facility
- Other (please specify)

3. The majority of my research is funded by ...

- An international grant
- A national grant
- Private sector funding
- No outside funding
- I don't have any funding for my research
- Other (please specify)

4. In the last 5 years I have published ...

- No papers in peer-reviewed journals
- 1 - 3 papers in peer-reviewed journals
- 4 - 5 papers in peer-reviewed journals
- Over 5 papers in peer-reviewed journals

5. Please enter the country that you work in

6. The “physical” research environment refers to the design, provisioning and maintenance of the laboratory. It also refers to the provision of services essential for scientific research. On a scale of strongly agree to strongly disagree, please rate the influence of the following factors on your ability to conduct research.

	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neither agree nor disagree	Agree	Strongly agree	N/A
Power outages challenge my ability to generate data	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Power outages challenge my ability to disseminate data	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Power outages challenge my ability to find and re-use data available online	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
The time taken to order and receive reagents challenges my ability to generate data	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
My laboratory lacks sufficient back-up for power outages and this affects my performance as a researcher	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
The lack of availability of adequate equipment for my research needs slows down my ability to generate data	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I cannot get the reagents I need for my research which slows down my ability to generate data	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neither agree nor disagree	Agree	Strongly agree	N/A
The lack of technical support for the equipment I use slows down my ability to generate data	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
The need to outsource analyses slows down my ability to generate data	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
The inability to adequately maintain equipment slows down my ability to generate data	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I lack sufficient storage space for samples and reagents	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I lack sufficient space to work and sharing workspaces slows down my research	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Sharing basic laboratory equipment such as Gilson Pipettes slows down my research	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
My laboratory does not have sufficient electrical plug points to run our equipment at the same time which slows down my research	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
My laboratory does not have sufficient laboratory assistance – waste disposal, cleaning, glassware maintenance, autoclaving - meaning that I have to do this, which slows down my research	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I lack up-to-date hardware	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I lack up-to-date software	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
The speed of the cable internet at my university slows down my online activities	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neither agree nor disagree	Agree	Strongly agree	N/A
The speed of the wifi at your university slows down my online activities	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I cannot access library resources off campus	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I do not have a good internet connection at home, which affects my online activities	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I have not had sufficient training in the use of information and communication technologies	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I have not had sufficient training conducting research online	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
English is not my first language and I experience language barriers in the online resources I would like to use	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I do not use my institutional repository	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I cannot access the journal articles that I want from my institutional library	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Other (please specify)	<input type="text"/>					

7. The financial and regulatory aspects of the research environment refer to the regulations that govern your research. On a scale of strongly agree to strongly disagree, please rate the influence of the following factors on your ability to conduct research.

	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neither agree nor disagree	Agree	Strongly agree	N/A
My institution does not have regulations about sharing data	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
My institution does not support data sharing activities financially	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neither agree nor disagree	Agree	Strongly agree	N/A
Data sharing is not part of promotion criteria	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
My institution does not support intellectual property protection financially	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
My institution does not support intellectual property protection with advice or support	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I do not have flexibility in the use of grant money to address core issues in my laboratory	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I lack funds to maintain and upgrade my laboratory environment	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I lack money to conduct research	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I lack the ability to spend the money I have in the ways that are most necessary for my research	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
National regulations do not support data sharing activities financially	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
National regulations do not exist for data sharing	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
National regulations are not comprehensive for intellectual property protection	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Other (please specify)	<input type="text"/>					

8. The collegial aspects of the research environment refer to personal and institutional influences that affect how you conduct research. On a scale of strongly agree to strongly disagree, please rate the influence of the following factors on your ability to conduct research.

	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neither agree nor disagree	Agree	Strongly agree	N/A
My teaching and supervision commitments slow down or stop my ability to spend time online contributing data	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
My teaching and supervision commitments slow down or stop my ability to spend time online finding relevant data	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
My teaching and supervision commitments slow down or stop my ability to generate research data	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I feel that I have not had sufficient training in conducting online research	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I feel that I have not had sufficient training in how to disseminate my data online	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I lack mentors that assist me with developing data engagement activities	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I have not had sufficient training in ways to promote my research online through altmetric pathways	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
The postgraduate student turnover in my department makes it difficult to retain and effectively use the data they generate	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
The number of postgraduate students that I supervise makes it difficult to coordinate data storage and curation	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neither agree nor disagree	Agree	Strongly agree	N/A
The broad focus of the student projects I oversee makes it difficult to collectively synthesise research findings	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I feel that my institution does not support research activities	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I do not receive support for data sharing and dissemination aside from publishing in peer-reviewed journals	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
The majority of my postgraduate students lack full-time scholarships	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
My department does not have web pages for individual staff members that detail their research interests and publications	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Other (please specify)	<input type="text"/>					

9. An important aspect of conducting research is the ability to contribute and receive data online. We will now ask you some questions relating to your online activities. First, could you clarify what you understand by the term: *Open Data*

10. Could you clarify what you understand by the term: *Open Access*

11. Now could you let us know what sort of online activities you are normally engaged with. Please check *all* the appropriate answers to the statement: *I regularly share data and publications via ...*

- Peer-reviewed publication
- Email with colleagues
- Altmetric websites such as Figshare or Twitter
- Professional networking sites such as ResearchGate
- Institutional repositories
- Online databases
- Other (please specify)

12. Please check *all* the appropriate answers to the statement: *I am comfortable sharing data with people that I know ...*

- Pre-publication
- Post-publication
- Only through publication
- Other (please specify)

13. Please check all the appropriate answers to the statement: *I am comfortable sharing data with people that I **don't** know ...*

- Pre-publication
- Post-publication
- Only through publication
- Other (please specify)

14. Please check an appropriate answer to the statement: *I believe the biggest benefit of sharing my own data is ...*

- The exposure that it brings my research
- That it contributes to the advancement of science
- That it brings networking and collaboration opportunities
- I don't believe there is a benefit for sharing my data
- Other (please specify)

15. Please check an appropriate answer to the statement: *My biggest concern about sharing my own data is ...*

- Having other researchers take my results
- Losing out on opportunities to maximize publications from my data sets
- Missing out on opportunities to maximize the intellectual property from my data sets
- Having my data mis-interpreted or mis-attributed
- Other (please specify)

16. Please check an appropriate answer to the statement: *My colleagues discuss ways to share data outside of peer-reviewed publications ...*

- Regularly
- Often
- Sometimes
- Rarely
- Never

17. Please check an appropriate answer to the statement: *My colleagues share data outside of peer-reviewed publications ...*

- Regularly
- Often
- Sometimes
- Rarely
- Never

18. Please use this space to briefly elaborate on how you think a sum of \$5000 could be used to address issues within your laboratory research environment that would have the most positive effect on your research.